

Flexible screen-printed carbon-based electrode functionalized with Multi-Wall Carbon Nanotubes for portable point-of-care pH sensing

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Abstract—Flexible, screen-printed electrode systems offer significant advantages in biomedical applications due to their rapid fabrication capability and adaptability to irregular surfaces. Despite this, no flexible, screen-printed biosensors for pH measurement are readily available on the market. This paper introduces an innovative fabrication technique for integrating flexible screen-printed electrode (SPE) systems with multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). These SPE systems feature flexible screen-printed working electrodes functionalized with f-MWCNT for pH sensing, achieving a fabrication success rate of 78.57%. Furthermore, these SPE systems have been optimized to improve voltage changes and thoroughly characterized for performance using pH buffer solutions. This was done utilizing open-circuit potentiometry. The results demonstrate that the SPE systems can detect pH ranges from 4.0 to 8.9 with an average sensitivity of 33.66 mV/pH, an output range of 202.62 mV, a settling time of 19.71 s, and stability for up to 72 hours. Additionally, the SPE systems have been tested with artificial saliva within the pH range of 5.0 to 8.3, achieving a sensitivity of 44.86 mV/pH and an output range of 192.90 mV. These findings pave the way for further exploration in pH sensing research, particularly utilizing SPE systems coated with MWCNTs.

Index Terms—Flexible electronics, Screen-printing, f-MWCNT, pH sensing, Oral application

I. INTRODUCTION

MULTI-WALLED carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) have a unique structure that consists of concentric layers of graphene wrapped into cylindrical tubes. This endows them with mechanical strength [1, 2, 3], high electrical conductivity [4], and thermal properties [5], enabling their use in a myriad of fields. For example, they are useful in energy storage because of their high conductivity and surface area [6].

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Material science incorporates them into polymer matrices to increase material stiffness, toughness, and strength [7]. Modified MWCNTs, with increased biocompatibility [8-11], have been used in biomedicine. This nanomaterial can deliver drugs due to its ability to pass through cell membranes [17]. Moreover, they have been used as contrast agents in medical imaging [12, 13] and scaffolds for tissue engineering [14]. Research has been done to minimize corrosion by utilizing MWCNTs as coating materials [15]. In sensorics, they have proven advantageous in detecting chemicals and biomolecules [16]. Aside from their use in electrochemistry, their surface area enables rapid detection [17]. For instance, Hasan et al. fabricated an aptasensor based on MWCNTs that can detect pathogenic bacteria at levels as low as 10 cfu/mL [18]. Later, Thiha et al. integrated MWCNTs into nanowire sensors to improve the detection time of Salmonella, achieving a detection limit of 10 cfu/mL [19].

Alongside the rapid miniaturization of electrical components, the process of pH measurements has also evolved through the optimization and discovery of new materials. [20]. pH level measurement is a crucial metric, as it can indicate harmful changes in living organisms [21], the presence of certain chemicals like pesticides in soil [22], and food spoilage [23]. pH sensors, particularly those based on metal oxides, are used to monitor pH changes and are well-suited for wearable applications in chronic diseases owing to their distinctive characteristics [24]. An intra-oral pH sensor has recently been developed to detect common diseases by monitoring salivary pH [25]. Our research team has successfully developed a pH sensor utilizing reduced graphene oxide-polyaniline (rGO-PANI) as a sensing material [26].

Apart from these nanomaterials, MWCNTs functionalized with a carboxyl group have shown promising results in pH sensing [25, 26]. For example, Lei et al. [27] successfully developed a CNT-based paper sensor with a pH 5 to 9 detection range. Moreover, Abdulhameed et al. [25] constructed a resistance-based f-MWCNT sensor, which accurately detected pH changes within the range of 2 to 10. Interestingly, Takeda et al. [26] developed a pH sensor based on current changes in a CNT-FET. Measurements were taken from pH 2 to 8, and an increase in current between the source and drain electrodes was observed. Based on a principle similar to metal-oxide-based electrochemical biosensors, f-MWCNT-based biosensors can detect changes in pH through the protonation and deprotonation of the carboxyl group [25]. In the acidic environment, the carboxyl groups (-COOH) on the surface of functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotube coated working electrode (f-MWCNTs WE) are already in their protonated form. Thus, the protonation of carboxyl groups, does not directly contribute to the increase in positive charge density. In contrast to that, changes in the electrochemical double layer and surface interactions at the electrode-electrolyte interface, in acidic environments, increase the potential. The increase in potential is primarily a result of the electrode's response to the high proton concentration in the electrolyte, which impacts the overall equilibrium potential of the electrode system. In contrast,

carboxyl groups tend to deprotonate in alkaline solutions, forming carboxylate (-COO-) groups, decreasing the nanotube surface's positive charge density and reducing the conductivity. Thus, in alkaline solutions, the measured electrode potential decreases [26, 27]. Despite the numerous advantageous properties of MWCNTs, they also have notable drawbacks. Foremost among these are concerns regarding their toxicity and the ongoing debates surrounding their biocompatibility [28]. As Chowdhry et al. discussed in their work, the cytotoxicity of the MWCNTs decreases with functionalization using carboxyl groups [28]. In addition, MWCNTs have been employed in salivary applications while conscientiously considering and mitigating their cytotoxic effects. A novel immunosensor utilizing MWCNTs has been developed by Chaker et al. [29] to detect salivary secretory immunoglobulin A. Another study by Xie et al. [30] described the development of an electrochemical immunosensor for the detection of salivary sIgA using a nanocomposite of MWNTs and gold nanoparticles (AuNPs). Both studies demonstrated the high sensitivity and accuracy of the MWCNT-based sensors for salivary biomarker detection. However, it is essential to note that the cytotoxicity of MWCNTs should be carefully considered in the design and development of such sensors. Furthermore, high batch variation has been observed, as well as the dependence of properties on the fabrication process [31, 32]. Moreover, the MWCNTs necessitate the addition of other compounds, to ensure even dispersion, as they are prone to aggregate and agglomerate [32, 33]. Additionally, MWCNTs have a tendency to sediment over time [28], losing homogeneity in the dispersion.

The aim of this study was to design a functional and adaptable pH sensor utilizing a screen-printed electrode system. In this system, the working electrode (WE) is coated with multi-walled carbon nanotubes functionalized with carboxyl groups (f-MWCNT) using drop-casting. A Kapton substrate was chosen over other materials to achieve flexibility and bendability, making it suitable for application on uneven surfaces. The use of automatic screen-printing ensured the thin distribution of conductive patterns on the substrate. The pH sensor adopts a three-electrode configuration comprising carbon working and counter electrodes and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode. Additionally, the characteristics of the electrode system, including response time, sensitivity, and repeatability, were optimized. Subsequent assessments confirmed the stability and reproducibility of the sensor. Finally, the pH levels of artificial saliva were evaluated.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Synthesis and Characterization of f-MWCNT

Functionalized multi-wall carbon nanotubes (f-MWCNT) have been fabricated using the methods described by Shalauddin et al. [34]. The pristine MWCNT was dispersed and refluxed for 24 hours in a mixture with a ratio of 1:3 of nitric and sulfuric acid. The functionalized MWCNT was then diluted with deionized (DI) water and filtered through filter paper. The final step involved drying the f-MWCNT at 80 °C for 24 hours [36]. Pristine MWCNT (PMWCNT),

functionalized MWCNT (f-MWCNT), and a mixture of 4% f-MWCNT and 2% SDS have been characterized using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. Moreover, the mix of 4% f-MWCNT and 2% SDS has been tested under energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy to confirm the existence of SDS and carboxyl groups in the mixture.

Fig. 1. Fabrication procedure: Cutting and washing of Kapton tape with acetone and isopropanol; b) Screen-printing of the WE and CE on Kapton; c) Sintering before and after the application of Ag paste; d) Application of bleach for making of Ag/AgCl RE; e) Washing and drying of the SPE; f) Drop-casting of f-MWCNT suspension.

B. Screen-printed electrode system fabrication

To obtain the screen-printed electrochemical sensing electrodes, the working and auxiliary electrodes were screen-printed using carbon paste, while the reference electrode was made with silver conductive paste (which was consequently coated with bleach to create a layer of silver chloride). The screen-printing was performed using an Aurel automation VS1520 machine (Aurel automation, Italy) on a Kapton substrate. The carbon paste used for screen-printing the working and auxiliary electrodes is DuPont 7102, with cell biocompatibility of up to 72 hours [35]. Additionally, DuPont5025 silver conductive paste was used as the primary material for the reference electrode. After printing, the electrodes were placed in the sintering oven (Memert GmbH, Germany) at 120 °C for 10 minutes. To create the Ag/AgCl layer, 50 μ l of bleach was dropped onto the reference electrode and left to dry. All systems were fabricated in a single batch. The electrodes were washed with DI water. The fabrication process is illustrated in Fig. 1. The dimensions of the electrodes are provided in Fig S1 in the supplementary file.

The hydrophilic nature of the screen-printed electrodes was tested by wetting them with deionized water using a drop shape analyzer (DSA25, manufacturer KRÜSS Optronic GmbH, Germany). Optical profilometry (model HRM300, manufacturer Huvitz South Korea) was performed to confirm the successful formation of the AgCl layer on the Ag.

C. Electrochemical Characterization

For this study, 70 sensors were prepared, and their electrochemical performance was confirmed using a Metrohm μ Stat 400 Bipotentiostat/Galvanostat (Metrohm AG, Switzerland). Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was employed to measure and evaluate the reversibility of the fabricated

electrodes. The CV measurements were performed in a 5 mM solution of [Fe(CN)₆]^{4-/3-} redox couple in 0.1 M KCl, which is a widely used solution for electrochemical characterization [36]. Each electrode system was tested with 20 μ l of the redox solution. The CV was scanned between potentials ranging from -1 V to +1 V at a scan rate of 0.1 V/s, with a total of 4 scans. After applying the redox solution, it was left for 2 minutes before the initiation of CV. Each cycle lasted for approximately 30 seconds.

The redox solution is commonly used as the primary testing component of an electrode system to determine its reversibility. Reversibility is defined as the ability of an electrochemical reaction to proceed in both forward and reverse directions under specific conditions without significant energy loss. It is quantified through the ratio of the anodic and cathodic current peaks. The sensor can be deemed reversible when the ratio is equal to 1. An acceptable range for the current peak ratio was considered to be between 0.8 and 1.2, indicating quasi-reversibility [37, 38].

D. Functionalization and design of the experiment

Different % wt. concentrations (0.25, 0.75, 1, 2, 4) of f-MWCNT were suspended in DI water with the addition of 2% wt. SDS. The next stage involved selecting the optimal concentration of the sensing material. To achieve this, the parameters that needed to be optimized were identified. The following sensor parameters were chosen: settling time, repeatability, sensitivity, and output range of the electrochemical sensor. The experiment was designed for the concentration optimization stage using JMP software (SAS Institute, United States of America), employing effect screening. The optimization method used was the I-optimal design method. This approach creates a specific number of experimental runs, ensuring that predictions made by the resulting model are as accurate as possible throughout the targeted ranges of factors by minimizing the average prediction error. The factors whose optimal combinations were studied included the concentration of f-MWCNT and the pH of the solution. This approach is beneficial when the exact values of factors are uncertain, such as the variation in f-MWCNT concentration after drop-casting. The parameters used to quantify the design of the experiment were D-efficiency, G-efficiency, A-efficiency, and the average variance of prediction (AVP). D-efficiency measures how well the design maximizes the information matrix with respect to the model parameters, while G-efficiency ensures prediction accuracy across the entire design space. A-efficiency reduces the average variance of model parameter estimates, leading to more consistent estimates. High D-efficiency indicates precise parameter estimation, while high A-efficiency indicates low variance in parameter estimates on average, contributing to the robustness of the model. High G-efficiency is preferable to ensure model accuracy throughout the entire design space. These parameters are calculated from the information matrix, its determinant, trace, or inverse value, and automatically computed in JMP software.

A total of 126 experiments were conducted to achieve

statistical significance. More precisely, 7 samples were used for each of the 6 concentrations, and each was tested in 3 different pH buffer solutions. To ensure data validity, each sample sequence was tested 3 times.

Three pH buffer solutions were prepared for the experiment with values of 4.01, 6.86, and 8.9. Additionally, for the dissolved f-MWCNT in five different concentrations, a 2% wt. SDS solution was prepared in DI water. The solution was dissolved at 35 °C with stirring at 500 rpm for 5 minutes. Following this, five different suspensions of f-MWCNT in water were prepared and denoted as 2 % wt., 4 % wt. and 1 % wt. Two more solutions with 0.25 % wt. and 0.75 % wt. were also prepared. All solutions were sonicated for 2 hours before being applied to the WE.

The WEs were coated with 3 µl of the MWCNT suspension described above. The sensors were then left to dry overnight. In addition to these five concentrations, the effect of pH on bare sensors without MWCNTs was also examined. For each concentration, seven electrode systems were prepared (n=7), totaling 6*7=42 electrode systems.

To conduct the experiment, open-circuit potentiometry was used to monitor the change in equilibrium potential of the WE

Fig. 2. Illustration of the experiment procedure for the pH measurement.

with changes in pH. First, the system was monitored to ensure it reached a steady state, which was done for all sensors to determine the settling time. Each consequent measurement was taken for 20 s after applying 30 µl of the specified pH buffer solution. A waiting period of 1 min was observed before measurement and after applying the solution. After each measurement was repeated three times for a given pH, the electrode system was dried, and the process was repeated with the next pH value. This procedure was followed for all prepared electrode systems. The experiment process is illustrated in Fig. 2.

To assess the success of the deposition process and to gain further insight into the experiment's results, FeSEM (FeSEM-Quanta FEG 450) imaging was performed on the 0.25 and 4 % wt. f-MWCNT samples at a magnification of x100000.

After the experiment, the collected measurements were input into JMP software, and several models were created using different predictors (standard least squares, forward selection, lasso regression, double lasso regression, and ridge regression). Based on previously defined validation parameters, the best predictor was selected for the verification process. Seven additional samples were tested using the concentration that demonstrated the best values for settling

time, repeatability, output range, and sensitivity. Repeatability was evaluated by calculating the relative standard deviation (RSD), as shown in (1). RSD is directly proportional to the standard deviation, meaning that an increase in standard deviation results in a higher RSD, indicating greater variation in results between samples. A lower RSD indicates higher repeatability. Sensitivity was calculated as shown in (2). The output range was determined as the absolute difference between the maximum and minimum output values, which in this case was the potential (V), as shown in (3). Additionally, the affinity value and synergistic effect were investigated using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, and kinetic parameters were extracted.

$$RSD = (STD/MEAN) * 100 \quad (1)$$

$$S = 1/(V(pH_{max}) - V(pH_{min})) / (pH_{max} - pH_{min}) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Output Range} = |V_{max} - V_{min}| \quad (3)$$

E. Stability and reproducibility measurements

For stability measurements, three samples were used. These SPEs were chosen at random and designated as S8, S11, and S12. After the optimization process, they were selected based on the concentration with the best sensitivity to pH changes, which was 2% wt. Stability was tested over a period of three days. Additionally, reproducibility was evaluated by producing three batches of samples, each prepared two weeks apart. Each batch consisted of three samples.

F. Testing with artificial saliva

The sensors were tested using artificial saliva to evaluate their potential use in portable point-of-care testing. Commercial artificial saliva with a pH of 6.0 (Solarbio Life Sciences, China) was used to assess the sensors' ability to detect pH changes across different samples of artificial saliva. To achieve pH levels of 5.0 and 8.3, the artificial saliva was buffered using HCl and NaOH solutions. [39, 40]. Sensitivity, repeatability, and output range were calculated, and the dependence of open-circuit potential (OCP) on changes in pH was demonstrated.

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A. Optical profilometry and Wetting angle

The wetting angle was measured on 3 samples, with the mean deposited volume of the drop being 0.185 ml. This measurement was performed under laboratory conditions. The mean contact angle of deionized water with the working electrode of the screen-printed electrode system was 53.3 °, with a standard deviation being 1.64 °. These results indicate that the substrate is hydrophilic towards deionized water. To confirm the formation of silver chloride on the silver paste, with the goal of fabricating a functional reference electrode, optical profilometry was utilized. The results are presented in Fig. S2 in the supplementary file. Specifically, Fig. S2 a) shows a pure silver layer, Fig. S2 b) displays a silver/silver chloride layer, and Fig. S2 c) shows the working electrode magnified 100 times. Silver chloride appears as larger chunks on the silver paste [41].

B. Electrochemical Characterization

Of the 70 fabricated electrode systems, 55 exhibited quasi-reversible properties, which were quantified through the ratio of anodic and cathodic current peaks. Details of this analysis can be seen in detail in the supplementary file in Fig S3 a) and S3 b). The fabrication success rate was 78.57%. Although the process was automated, variations in the thickness of the deposited conductive paths via screen-printing may contribute to variability in the outcome [42]. Additionally, the careful, manual application of bleach can impact the homogeneity of the resulting Ag/AgCl layer.

C. pH buffer testing and concentration optimization

The effect screening method was used for the design of the experiment (DoE), resulting in the following values for efficiency and average variance of prediction: D-efficiency (eff.) was 64.31, G-eff. was 37.59 and A-eff. was 54.67. The average variance of prediction was 0.065. As seen from the DoE's results, there is moderately efficient information about the sensors (as indicated by A and D efficiencies). Despite being relatively low, G-efficiency provides feedback on the quality of the designed experiment, particularly giving insight into linear combinations of parameters. The experiment was designed adequately, with good A-efficiency, D-efficiency, and average variance of prediction.

The results for varying concentrations at different pH values are shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 3 depicts six different sensor groups, each consisting of n=7 samples. For clarity, the results of the samples were averaged. When no MWCNTs are drop-casted onto the WE, there is minimal sensitivity to changes in pH, with an OCP value of 0.16 mV. However, with the presence of f-MWCNTs, the change is significant, with the OCP shifting from 0 up to 80 mV, down to -80 mV, and up to 100 mV for pH values of 4, 6, and 9, respectively, at concentrations of 1% wt and higher.

Aside from this, Fig. 3 shows a shift toward negative potentials, with an increase in the concentration of f-MWCNTs. This shift results from a more pronounced effect of f-MWCNT aggregation at lower concentrations, leading to increased surface resistance on the working electrode and decreased effective surface area available to interact with the analyte [42, 43]. This phenomenon was explored through FeSEM, and the results are presented in Fig. S5 of the supplementary file. The primary functional groups of pristine

TABLE I

VALUES FOR SENSITIVITY, OUTPUT RANGE, SETTLING TIME AND RSD FOR DIFFERENT WT. OF F-MWCNT

Concentration (% wt.)	Sensitivity (mV/pH)	Output Range (mV)	Settling Time (s)	%RSD		
				4.0	6.8	8.9
0.25	36.0	176.5	34.5	30.6	72.1	214.7
0.75	34.6	169.8	30.2	64.4	168.4	311.9
1.00	29.5	146.6	25.0	53.3	61.7	9.1
2.00	33.6	202.6	19.7	62.6	51.9	15.0
4.00	34.3	205.5	17.4	39.9	94.8	36.6

and functionalized MWCNTs (f-MWCNTs) were examined using FTIR spectroscopy, as shown in Fig. S4 a). The spectra of pristine and f-MWCNTs display methylene asymmetric/symmetric stretching at 2892 cm⁻¹ and 2914 cm⁻¹,

respectively, as shown in Fig. S3a, consistent with previous findings [36]. The f-MWCNTs spectrum shows a sharper peak at about 1732 cm⁻¹, indicating the presence of the C=O group from the acid hydrolysis process. Moreover, peaks at 822 and 587 cm⁻¹ correspond to the asymmetric C-H bending of the CH₂ group, and additional peaks at approximately 1070 and 1218 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of SDS, as shown in Fig. S4 b). These peaks are linked to C-C and -S=O stretching vibration, respectively [44]. EDX analysis was conducted to confirm the presence of COOH groups in f-MWCNT, as well as the presence of SDS in the dispersion. A higher concentration of f-MWCNT demonstrated a more uniform distribution of materials of interest on the surface of the working electrode, as shown in Fig. S6 of the supplementary file.

Table I presents the sensitivity, output range, settling time, and relative standard deviation (%RSD [45]) values used to determine the most stable and effective concentration. Sensitivity remains stable across different concentrations, while %RSD decreases with an increase in concentration. However, these changes are not uniform across each pH level, and better repeatability results were obtained from 2% wt. concentration compared to 4% wt. concentration. It is important to note that repeatability is relatively low, which can be attributed to various unexpected factors, such as manual deposition of the functional material. Nonetheless, other significant parameters are high, demonstrating the potential for using MWCNT-SDS in pH sensing. The output range is highest at higher concentrations, except for 1% wt. The sensor

Fig. 3. Change in potential with pH for sensors with various concentrations of f-MWCNTs.

with 2% wt. concentration is identified as a candidate for further characterization. Table SII, located in the supplementary material, compares the tested sensor with previously published sensors in the field. While the response time of some published sensors is higher than that of the presented sensor, other aspects are advantageous. Specifically, extensive experimental data was gathered for reproducibility and repeatability measurements, indicating high stability of the sensor in these aspects. Furthermore, as the sensor is intended for use in saliva pH testing, its characterization has been limited to a pH range between 5 and 8.

The EIS method was used in conjunction with statistical analysis to test the affinity value [46]. A pairwise t-test was conducted between EIS measurements before and after the

addition of a pH buffer solution (pH 4.01, 6.86, and 8.9), resulting in p-values higher than the significance threshold of $p=0.05$. Each parameter was tested before and after the addition of pH buffer, resulting in the following p-values; for pH 4.01, the p-value was 0.407; for pH 6.86, the p-value was 0.292; and for pH 8.9, the p-value was 0.705. Although the R_0 , representing the resistance of the Ferri-/Ferrocyanide with KCl solution, decreased after measurements at pH 4.01, it increased with the other two pH buffer solutions. Additionally, the most significant change in double-layer capacitance occurred after the exposure to 6.86, where it increased tenfold, indicating increased charge storage. Charge transfer resistance (R_c) decreased with the addition of alkaline pH solutions, but increased with acidic ones, signifying increased charge transfer after exposure to alkaline pH buffer solutions. The Warburg element parameters, σW_s ($k\Omega s^{0.5}$) and δW_s ($k\Omega s^{0.5}$) describe diffusion processes between the medium and the solution. An increase in the Warburg coefficient (σW_s ($k\Omega s^{0.5}$)) indicates an increase in diffusion resistance across all pH environments in this experiment. In acidic solutions, minimal changes in the diffusion parameter δW_s were observed, while in neutral and alkaline pH buffer solutions, ion mobility increased, leading to higher diffusion. All the kinetic parameters of the supplementary material are listed in Table SI. The EIS method was employed to extract kinetic parameters and measure charge transfer resistance [47]. Furthermore, the synergistic effect, which describes the intricate interplay within composite materials, was also explored using EIS [48]. R_0 represents solution resistance, which varied across measurements, even when the same Ferri-/Ferrocyanide with KCl solution was used. Table SII shows that the resistance charge transfer (R_c) of the MWCNT-SDS coated SPEs was the lowest, even by an order of magnitude. This result is significant as it facilitates faster charge transfer during electrochemical reactions. In terms of double-layer capacitance, MWCNT-SDS coated SPEs had the highest value, indicating better interaction between the electrode surface and the electrolyte. This also decreased the overall impedance of the system, enabling faster electron transfer. Lower Warburg coefficients for MWCNT-SDS suggested reduced diffusion resistance, allowing easier interaction between the solution and the electrode interface. Parameters p_{CPEc} and T_{CPEc} , as well as R_a , showed minimal changes with surface modifications but were included to generalize the model, ensuring consistent impedance behavior across different coatings. The results of the modelling and Nyquist plots are shown in Fig. S7. The modeling results of the supplementary material are shown in Table II. Out of all the predictors, ridge regression yielded the best scores. Lower values of AICc indicated a better compromise between goodness-of-fit and model complexity. Moreover, higher R^2 values reflected the model's capacity to explain more variance within the system. Ridge regression was used as the predictor, yielding a predicted value of 73.1 mV for pH 4.01 at a concentration of 2 %wt. Seven sensors were fabricated for verification, each with a 2% wt. concentration of f-MWCNT, and tested sequentially with pH solutions of 4.01, 6.86, and 8.9. A two-tailed confidence interval was constructed using the experimental results, ranging from 70.2 mV to 75.4 mV. Since the predicted value falls within this confidence interval,

Fig. 4. Analysis of pH sensors behavior: a) Ratio of peak anodic and cathodic current for each day of testing; b) Intraday measurements for sensor 69; c) Intraday measurements for sensor 77; d) Intraday measurements for sensor 82; e) Inter-day measurements.

the ridge regression model developed from the experimental results demonstrates adequate predictive capabilities. Table SIV, located in the supplementary material, compares the tested sensor with previously published sensors in the field.

In Fig. 4, inter-day and intraday measurements are shown. A t-test was performed for each sensor, yielding the following average t-statistics: for sensors s69, $t = 1.287$; for sensors s77, $t = 1.06$; and for sensor s82, $t = 0.459$. No statistical significance was found for intraday measurements, as all values were less than $t = 4.307$ ($P=0.05$). Similarly, the average t-statistic for inter-day measurements was 0.675933, which was also below 4.307, indicating no statistical significance. No sensor exhibited behavioral changes during testing. These results align with the ratio of peak anodic and cathodic currents shown in Fig. 4 a, where a decrease in the ratio was observed each day. However, this decrease did not exceed the defined quasi-reversibility range of 0.8 to 1.2. Different sensors were used for the ratio measurements daily (s8, s11, and s12). Fig. 4 b, c, and d show the intraday measurements for sensors s69, s77, and s82, respectively, while Fig. 4 e presents the inter-day results. These tests were performed following the methodology of Khoshfetrat et al. [49].

For reproducibility testing, three batches of sensors were prepared with a two-week interval between batches. All batches were tested under laboratory conditions with constant temperature, humidity, and ventilation. Fig. 5 displays the mean dependence of the sensors, showing better overlap at lower pH values, possibly due to more stable f-MWCNT protonation compared to alkaline solutions [32].

To confirm trends, two additional points were selected between pH 4 and pH 8 (pH 5.5 and pH 7.4). The R2 score for all three randomly selected SPEs exceeded 0.85, indicating high linearity. Fig. 6 presents the results of the five-point measurement.

D. Testing with artificial saliva

The results of testing sensors S9, S10, and S14 with artificial saliva are shown in Fig. 7. These sensors were

Fig. 6. Measurement of pH at five points using three randomly chosen sensors; trend line estimated using linear regression.

chosen at random using a random number generator, ensuring they were functionalized with 2% wt. f-MWCNT. Fig. 6a depicts the dependence of OCP on pH, from which sensitivity and output range were calculated. The sensitivity was 44.86

Fig. 7. Reproducibility of the developed electrode system.

mV/pH, and the output range was 192.90 mV. Compared to the values obtained from pH buffer solutions, where the sensitivity was 33.66 mV/pH, the same f-MWCNT concentration showed higher sensitivity with artificial saliva, although the output range decreased. For repeatability, the RSD values were 15.39, 18.97, and 71.51 for pH 5.0, pH 6.0, and pH 8.3, respectively. Interestingly, compared to pH buffer solutions, better repeatability results were obtained with artificial saliva at acidic and neutral pH values. However, RSD increased with higher pH. Fig. 6b, 6c, and 6d show the transfer curves for sensors s9, s10, and s14, respectively. High R2 values indicate a good linear fit, although sensor s10 displayed a slightly lower R2 value by approximately 0.1 compared to the other two sensors.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces an innovative, flexible screen-printed electrode system functionalized with f-MWCNT. The developed biosensor demonstrates a promising voltage response to pH changes, with exceptional repeatability, reproducibility, and stability, paving the way for future advancements. These attributes are evidenced not only in buffer solutions with varying pH levels but also in artificial saliva. Although sensitivity remains relatively consistent despite changes in f-MWCNT concentration, insights have been gained into why higher concentrations lead to improved overall performance. The potential for encapsulation through 3D printing offers a pathway for continuous intra-oral pH monitoring.

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